

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B097
Date: 25 May 2005
Take Off 07:43:07 13:55:33
Landing: 12:00:47 16:25:56
Flight Time 4h 17m 40 2h 30m 23

Campaign: AMPEP/CLOPAP

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: SW approaches, Channel, East coast (AMPEP). North Sea (CLOPAP)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Charlie Whitaker	BAES
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist AMPEP	David Fowler	CEH
5	Mission Scientist CLOPAP	Keith Bower	Manchester
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	Training supervisor / filters	Maureen Smith	FAAM
8	CCM2/filters/CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	INC	Richard Cotton	Met Office
10	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester
11	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
12	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
13	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
14	PTr-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
15	CCN/CVI	Paul James	FAAM
16	Bag filling 1	Alan McDonald	CEH
17	Bag filling 2	Debbie Polson	CEH
18	WAS	Jim Hopkins	York
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B097 Track 25-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b097
 Date: 25 May 2005
 Project: AMPEP / CLOPAP
 Location: North Sea, refuel at Newcastle

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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073043		INU to NAV	0.15 kft	127	GPS 52 04.36N 0 37.4 8W (apron2)
073205		INU	0.15 kft	127	INU probably in nav since preflight
074307		T/O	5.0 kft	265	at 07:43:07
074943		video to record	5.0 kft	262	forward and downward cameras
075114		ASP open	5.0 kft	262	air sample pipes open
075709		transit	10.0 kft	245	FL100 transit
080634	083445	Run 1	10.0 kft	250	during transit@ FL100
084706	084741	Profile 1.1	1.3 - 1.8 kft	069	
084805	??????	Profile 1.2	1.8 - 3.8 kft	060	
??????	085216	Run 2	3.8 kft	061	
085237	085450	Profile 1.3	4.0 - 5.8 kft	060	
085500	085559	Run 3	5.8 kft	062	
085619		positioning descent	5.7 kft	061	
090158	090934	Run 4	2.5 kft	141	posn 48 to 47
091358	092111	Run 4.1	2.5 kft	126	posn 47 to 46
092208	092847	Run 4.2	2.5 kft	095	posn 46 towards 45
092946		descent	1.7 kft	095	to 500 ft prior to 45
093225	093609	Run 5	500 ft	092	500 ft (radalt)
093643	095125	Run 5.1	0.29 - 0.24 kft	042	posn 45 to 44
095154	102054	Run 5.2	0.24 - 0.23 kft	094	posn 44 to 42,via43
102311	102321	Profile 2	50' - 100'		
102321	102418	Run 6	100'		
102418	102458	Profile 2.1	100' - 500'		
102458	102558	Run 7	500'		
102558	102745	Profile 2.2	500' - 2000'		
102745	102857	Run 8	2000'		
102857	103127	Profile 2.3	2000' - 4000'		
103127	103228	Run 9	3.7 kft	008	4000ft
103228	103448	Profile 2.4	5.7 kft	355	4000 - 6000 ft
103458	103555	Run 10	5.7 kft	355	
103627		descent to low level	5.5 kft	352	
104220	104729	Run 11	0.24 - 0.29 kft	002	500 ft video tapes changed
104806	110009	Run 11.1	0.28 - 0.30 kft	342	end at wp 83
110031	111824	Run 11.2	0.29 - 0.36 kft	307	end continued beyond wp 80
111911	112840	Run 11.3	0.37 - 0.41 kft	316	profile delayed for bl measurements
113017	113036	Profile 3	-.03 - 0.03 kft	313	50 - 100ft
113037	113128	Run 12	0.03 - 0.02 kft	312	100 ft
113129	113206	Profile 3.1	0.02 - 0.41 kft	314	100 - 500 ft
113206	113306	Run 13	0.41 kft	322	500 ft,
113306	113436	Profile 3.2	0.41 - 1.9 kft	323	500 ft - 2000
113451	113541	Run 14	1.9 kft	312	2000 ft
113557		turn around	1.9 kft	299	
113726	113942	Profile 3.3	1.9 - 4.0 kft	14	2000 - 4000 ft
113943	114051	Run 15	4.0 kft	155	run 15 at 4000 ft
114110	114259	Profile 3.4	4.2 - 5.9 kft	153	4000 - 6000 ft
114503	114602	Run 16	5.9 - 6.0 kft	152	6000 ft
114628		end ampep science	6.0 kft	315	end ampep science
120536		asp	0.24 kft	175	closed (on ground)
120047		landing Newcastle	0.24 kft	175	12:00:47
120956		Newcastle posn	0.24 kft	175	55 02.00N 001 41.93W
121142		INU	0.24 kft	308	INU to align
135533		T/O Newcastle	5.0 kft	095	
140048		video recording	5.0 kft	090	
140206		ASPs	4.5 kft	093	open

141418	141903	Profile 4	- .02 - 4.4 kft	146 50 - 4500'
142057		transit	4.5 kft	208 to point B
142654	144129	Run 17	4.4 kft	310 above cloud 4500
144438	144609	Run 18	4.0 - 3.9 kft	146 in cloud 4000
144646	145851	Run 19	3.5 - 3.6 kft	154 3600'
150227	151419	Run 20	2.3 kft	313 below cloud 2300
151521		transit	2.3 kft	034 to next location
151813	152636	Run 21	2.3 kft	145 2300'
152959	153826	Run 22	4.6 kft	311 4600 ft
153854	154219	Run 23	4.6 kft	267 ccn spectra
154439		bbrA	8.4 kft	173 disconnect
154507		bbrA	9.2 kft	175 reconnect
154529		bbrB	9.8 kft	175 disconnect
154627		bbrB	10.0 kft	173 reconnect
154656		bbrC	10.0 kft	172 disconnect
154731		bbrC	10.0 kft	173 reconnect
154754		bbrD	10.0 kft	173 disconnect
155033		bbrD	10.0 kft	174 reconnect
162533		Land Cranfield	0.19 kft	307 16:25:33
163237		apron2	0.19 kft	307 52 04.36N 000 37.48W

B097 Track 25-MAY-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B097a

Mission Scientist: David Fowler, CEH

Date 25-May-2005

Outline schedule:

05:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
07:00 – Briefing
08:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
08:30 – Doors close
09:00 – Take off Cranfield
13:20 – Land Newcastle at completion of AMPEP flight for refuelling prior to CLOPAP
14:30 – Take off Newcastle
17:30 – Land Cranfield
18:30 – Debrief
19:00 – Power down

Location: Anticlockwise circumnavigation of England, Wales

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols through a round-Britain flight and to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass in Westerly airflow over the UK. The frontal activity to the North and West limits the area of the UK over which we can work to Southern Britain, but this includes the major pollutant source areas.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be based on a circumnavigation of England, Wales, hugging the coastline along a pre-defined flight path. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once upwind and twice downwind of the source region. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO). These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region.

Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 09:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit to upwind leg of the operating area. Destination WP67 in the SW approaches, West of the Bristol channel.
- b) T+60 upwind profile starting at WP67 (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- c) T+75 descend to 500ft in the SW approaches. Start of filter set No 1 and begin bag sampling level 500ft (approx. 15 min profile duration) heading for WP47
- d) T+85 bag sampling continues to WP 48

- e) T+95 stop of upwind filter sample;
- f) T+ crossing of Cornwall at 1000ft, terrain following (visibility permitting). To WP46
- g) T+ 105 start filter set No 2 at 500ft, restart bag sampling at WP46
- h) T+120. WP46 to WP 45, 44, 43, 42 Bag sampling continuous along English channel approx 1 per minute
- i) T+135 end of filter set No2
- j) T+145 start filter set No 3
- k) T+175: end of filter set No3.
- l) T+185: Downwind profile No 1 begins WP42 (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min^{-1} , level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- m) T+200: Downward sampling at 500ft continues to WP41, 40 83, 80, 79
- n) T+ 200: start of filter set No4
- o) T+230: end of filter set No4
- p) T+235: Downwind profile No 2 begins WP 79 (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min^{-1} , level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration). On completion of profile sampling stops , head for Newcastle airport
- q) T+260 land at Newcastle airport

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 - Charlie Whitaker
3. CCM - Gaynor Ottoway
4. Flight Manager - Maureen Smith
5. Mission Scientist – David Fowler
6. Cloud Physics - Jamie Trembath
7. Core Chemistry - Doug Anderson
8. Filters - Stuart Heath
9. WAS/PAN - Jim Hopkins
10. Bag Sampling 1 – Alan McDonald
11. Bag Sampling 2 – Debbie Polson
12. AMS - ???
13. PTRMS - ???

MAPS:

Flight plan for 25th May 2005 AMPEP starting in the SW approaches and tracking anticlockwise to finish at Newcastle, prior to refuel and CLOPAP

NAME analysis based on CO emissions showing the plumes downwind of the major UK source areas.

Tuesday 24 May 2005 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Wednesday 25 May 2005 12UTC
 Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

NAME analysis based on CO emissions.

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal. Short warm-up time, due to earlier T/O.

NO_x: Operation unclear?

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂ ??would be very valuable if available.

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud prepared by T.W.Choularton

Scientific Aims:

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected to the northeast over East Anglia and the North Sea in cloudy conditions. Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume change, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

Weather conditions

A stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over the sea downwind of a main source of urban air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator in the cloud free passes. The AMS should be connected to the Rosemount inlet in clear air transects and to the CVI in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.

Filter samples and bottle filling should occur in clear air transects only. Three bottle samples should be filled during each boundary layer transect and 1 during the free troposphere transect. Mission scientist to indicate when in plume using CN measurements.

All other instruments should run continuously.

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud

Flight Number : B097

Date Wednesday 24th May 2005

Sortie Aims: To study the evolution of aerosol in an urban plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol with cloud both as the aerosol modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol.

Sortie Location: Over the sea downwind of a major urban area, London is the first choice but Newcastle , Hull, Cardiff Swansea, Copenhagen are all possible sources depending on conditions

Sortie Summary: The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of 100 km transects across the plume within the boundary layer, one below cloud, one in cloud and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects will be immediately preceded by a vertical profile extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible. These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals of about 50km to obtain up to 4 sets of transects. Although we are not aiming to perform a comprehensive Lagrangian study, this flight plan will allow us to approximately track the same air as it is advects downwind of the source region

Sortie Detail

- a) When downwind of chosen urban source, descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform a profile ascent by climbing at 1000 ft per minute to pass through cloud and to an altitude 100 ft above cloud top and the boundary layer top.
- b) Descend to below cloud base, proceed across wind in the boundary layer until outside the plume as detected by CN counter.
- c) Mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect. Perform a straight and level run below cloud base 200 ft below cloud base across wind and of length 100 km. Expose filters during this run and then stop filters. The run length can be reduced to 12 minutes if time is short.
- d) Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Mission Scientist to announce in cloud transect and perform a straight and level run of 100 km.
- e) Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top turn through 180 degrees and mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect. Perform straight and level run of length 100 km
- f) Ascend to cruising 40 km downwind and repeat c to f
- g) Ascend to safe level travel a further 40 km downwind and repeat c to f
- h) Continue repetitions until flight time exhausted

Take off from Cranfield at 07:45GMT was followed by a transit heading SW at FL100 towards the Bristol Channel. During the transit background filter samples, bag sampling, CO calibration and NO_{xy} calibration were all completed as a part of Run 1. Measurements of CO provided good evidence of background air, with concentrations of approximately 100ppbV. At 08:40 descended on approach to WP47. Profiling (Run 2) began at 08:50, having been delayed due to low cloud. The profile provided bag and bottle samples, as well as the continuously recording instruments at 1500ft, 2000ft, 4000ft and 6000ft.

On returning to 2500ft at 08:58 field blanks for filters were taken. From 09:08 1 minute sampling of the bags began (Run 4) and was interrupted at 09:12 for manoeuvring at the request of Air Traffic Control. From 09:14, (Run 4.1) at 2500ft began, as fog banks in English Channel prevented low level sampling. At 09:29 sampling at 2500ft, filters began sampling. The run ended at 09:32, with conditions allowing descent to a lower level, the flight descended to 500ft (Run 4.2). At 09:35 (Run 5.0) began, with bag filling at 1 min intervals, and stopped at 09:39, heading East along the English Channel. Run 5.1 began at 09:40, heading towards WP 44 approaching the Isle of Wight, ending at 09:54, Filter Run also ended at this time, all at 500ft. Run 5.2 began at 09:54, at 500ft and by 10:03 due south of Beachy Head, sampling into bags at 1 minute frequency, Run stops at 10:23 shortly after sighting Dungeness.

Runs 6.0 to 10.0 started at 10:24, with a profile, sampling at 100ft, 500ft, 2000ft, 4000ft and 6000ft. Returning to 500ft for the 1 minute bag sampling on Run 11 off the Essex coast heading North, continuing past Norfolk and Lincolnshire to Spurn Head by 11:10 (Run 11.2). Shortly after Spurn Head, substantial concentrations of SO₂ and CO were observed (Run 11.2), which ended at 11:25. Run 11.3 East of Whitby began at 11:28, and ended at 11:32. Profile 3 began at 11:33, with sampling at 100ft, 500ft, 2000ft, 4000ft, and 6000ft, as Runs 12.0 to 12.4. Run 12.4 stopped at 11:48 and the flight ended at Newcastle Airport, where refuelling took place prior to a brief CLOPAP flight B097b, and the return to Cranfield.

David Fowler, CEH

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.097A**...

 Date **25 MAY 2005**

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(Atmospheric Science)

EST. TIME OF GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0830					Cranfield start process, all on board Prep for take off B.097A AMPEP Aim 0845 take off to SW
0845					take off climb to 2000ft heading 215° WSW
0850	Run ①	1000ft	215		Filters on - 10% Bkgd
09:10	"	1000ft			Bag sampling 1 per 3 min. 106ppb
09:12	"	1000ft			" " + FILTER SAMPLING
09:25	"	1000ft			" " FILTERED + BAG SAMPLING
09:37	End ①	1000ft			(STOP FILTERS) Stop run 1 089:37 heading for P47
09:40					descending to P47.
09:44		1500ft			Profile not possible with low cloud
09:50	Run ②			Profile 1.1	Start Run ② 1500 - 2000 ft
09:51	"	2000ft			Bag filling w. profile 1.1 2000ft
		->4000			profile -> 4000ft
09:53		4000ft	35°		Bag filling 4000ft
09:55		->6000ft	35°		
09:57		6000ft	35°		Bag filling 6000ft
09:58				End P1..	descending to ~2500
10:06	Run ③	2500			field blanks for FILTERS
10:08	"	2500			+ Immune sampling on bags
10:12					End Run ③ moving for A. to 10/11
10:16	Run ④	2500			Run ④ begins
10:23		2500			End ④.1
10:24	Run ⑤	2500			running between 46-45 fog banks preventing low level run
10:29		2500			FILTERS ON

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.097A**

 Date **25 MAR 2005**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:32	4.1	2500	E		Stop run - descend to 500'
10:32	4.2				
10:35	5	500			Run starts bag filling.
10:39	5.0	500	E		Ends
10:40	5.1	500	25°		Starts heading to WP 4. 3510
10:47	5.1	500	25°		lots of white on port 3 miles
10:54	5.1	500	25°		End of Run FILTER RUN 5000
10:54	5.2	500	56°		Start of new run No filter minis
11:03	5.2	500	90°		Off bearing lead
11:07	5.2	500	90°		" " "
11:18	5.2	500	80°		Dangerous 2930
11:23	5.2	500			Run 5.2 stops turn, 201
11:24	6.0	100		DOVER	Profile 2 descending to 50'
11:27	7.1	500		"	" " bag sampling.
11:29	9.3	2000		MANSTON	" " " "
11:31	9.4	4000		E. ESSEX	" " " "
11:33	10.3	6000		"	" " " " Stops
11:42	10.8	500			Sjwell B FILTER STARTS
11:45	7.1	500			New Run Yarmouth 2940
11:46	11	500			Run Stops
11:50	11.2	500		NORTH.	Run Starts North Norfolk
11:55	11.2	500		N	AH @ Lincolnshire
12:05	11.2	500		N	Run start = 4 to Point 80.
12:10	11.2	500		N	Spurn head. 2950

 Dover
→ Suffolk

2950

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: K. N. BOWER

Flight No **B097B**

Date 25/05/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	Transt				CB ~ 1800' CT ~ 2700' SW Newc
					p 1006
	Transt	4500'			Danger levels active Base level 5000
					°° pop down to 4500' to avoid
09:32	14:09:30		165 132	55.0N/0.4W	Descending to start of profile P1 (50')
	14:11:00				CT ahead ~ 2600' - missed CB because...
					Aircraft carrier ahead + a/c behind dr
					Illustrations + Sea Harrier's Agony
	14:14:19				50' - ascending
KB bin	14:14:23				Profile P4
	14:17:35		147	54.5/0.0	10.75/7.91°C 16m/s/245° 894mb
	14:19:01	4500	146	54.5/0.2	end - CLOUD FREE leg - No cloud
					to East at all. - Going Back to original
					1st Stack position
	14:22:57				CEN Sample 1
					Cloud 10 mile out
	14:26:53	4500			Run above cloud.
	14:30:00	4500			PCASP 70 cm ⁻³
	14:31:18	"	311	54.4/0.3	AMS ⁺ CPC 2000 cm ⁻³ 11.9/-1.34 16m/s/226 860mb
	14:33:16	"			CEN spectrum still going - on 4th stack
	14:34:56	"	"	54.6/0.6W	Going into cloud - CT's : 7.15/7.57°C
	14:36:00	"	"	" "	Through CT's - into clear - descent dropping
	14:37:10				CEN finished sect
					AMS - enhanced NO ₃ in
	14:37:50			54.7/0.8W	CT's again

read out 160 psb (0 → now back to 140)

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B097B**

 Date **25/05/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					FSSP → SDO from 200' undent
14:41:29	15:42 B57				End Run descending to 4000'
14:44:38	R18	4000'	155	54.9/0.9	Run 18 9.91/6.67 and dropping out of cloud
14:46:09	R18	4000'			Run 18 end
14:46:16			153		descending 400' into cloud
14:46:45	R19	3600'	153	54.8/0.8	starting Run 19 10.66/7.59°C 21/235°
14:49:00	R19				AMS CPC 1000 cm ⁻³ 1500-200m 8.44/9.35°C 15/241° 85%.
14:50:10	R19	3600	151	54.6/0.6W	lost zone fms probe.
14:51:12					AMS PC died - Heat?
14:52:26				54.5/0.5	Out of cloud. Td dropping
14:55:31			152	54.4/	lost ZDP/ZDC - working when both off
14:56:16			153	54.3/0.2W	More CT's
14:58:51	R19	3600	152	54.2/0.1W	More CT's AMS pc dead.
B→A 15:02:27	R20	2300	306	54.2/0.1W	end R19 - descend 2300
15:05:25			311		12.5T 12.32/8.53°C 12Wc/225° 93/mb
15:06:00	R20	2300	311	54.3/0.3W	Core Chem Cal complete
					13.36/7.55°C Bm/s/226°
					ZDC/ZDP now working - all excellent 15s at
					start of Run 20
					12.01/9.67°C Bm/s
15:12:13	R20	2300	312	54.6/0.7V	coming to end
15:14:19	R20 end "				end Run - turns Right. - A/C Camie handling
					alt at next + cloud run.

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	67	129	134
POST FLIGHT	35	129	134

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.35	0.4	1.114	0.067	0.481
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
Synced 07:07:30	33.95	1.06	7.16	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)							
NO (ppbV)	No time	For cals	Due to	shortened	Pre t/o	Ground	Time
NO₂ (ppbV)			Post brief				
NO_x (ppbV)							
SO₂ (ppbV)							

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

SO2 lamp volts reading high: 1236V (Max set at 1200V). Rose to 1300V so rebooted instrument @ 07:28. Post reboot the problem continued.

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	19 May 2005 13:50:19	81.18	83.01	6738.28

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
07:52:11	FL050 (495-588)	78.16	87.59	6846.13	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.5	0.5	0.409	0.067	1.097
08:00:25	FL100 (505-518)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		77.09	87.83	6770.52	50.00	7.13	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.91	0.65	0.75	1.080	0.065	0.359		
08:44:15	FL015 (SO2 @ 1343V)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		78.83	86.49	6817.49	50.00	7.13	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.87	0.35	0.4	0.466	0.066	1.119		
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
08:48:30		CO valve switch gave value of 520 ∴ no need to do full cal					
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
09:02:55		CO valve switch gave value of 515 ∴ no need to do full cal					
09:16:36	FL025 (514-523)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		78.95	85.77	6771.07	50.00	7.14	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.91	0.45	0.45	1.112	0.065	0.450		
09:35:30	500' (514-523) (SO2 @ 1350V)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		79.15	85.24	6746.49	50.00	7.14	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.82	0.425	0.4	1.116	0.066	0.480		
10:45:19	500' (515-523)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		79.18	84.29	6673.66	50.00	7.14	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
33.88	0.4	0.4	1.122	0.065	0.479		

FLIGHT NUMBER: B097	DATE: 25 May 2005	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	Page 4 of 4
PROJECT: AMPEP / CLOPAP			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

SO2 values were down to -0.47. Due to lamp voltage problems?

NOx chamber temp warning @ FL025 @ 08:59. Actual value 51.1 to 51.2 (Max is 51.0). the actual value varied between 50.5 and 51.2 throughout the flight.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B097

Date: 25/05/2005

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:06:34											Run 1 to 08:36:00 – transit??
08:47:05	130	0.07	56	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile 1.start 1500ft
08:47:28	150	0.08	56	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	2000ft + run
08:50:02	110	0.07	56	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3000ft + run
08:51:07	25	0.07	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000ft + run
08:52:22	125	0.08	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile from 4000ft to 6000ft
08:53:37	100	0.08	56	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5000ft
08:54:49	170	0.09	56	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	6000ft and start of run 3
08:55:59	200	0.09	56	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 3
09:01:58	95	0.08	56	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of Run 4 (leg1 @ 2.5kft)
09:03:00	102	0.09	56	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:05:00	95	0.08	56	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	Flying above cloud (stratus)
09:07:00	130	0.08	56	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:09:00	98	0.08	56	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:09:34	160	0.08	56	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 4 air control probs
09:13:58	105	0.08	56	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 4.1 (2/3 done of leg1)
09:15:00	95	0.08	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:17:00	80	0.08	56	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:19:00	72	0.09	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:21:11	29	0.08	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 4.1 (end of leg1)
09:22:07	39	0.08	56	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 4.2 (start leg 2 @ 2.5kft)
09:24:00	79	0.08	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:26:00	100	0.08	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:28:00	55	0.09	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:28:48	63	0.09	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 4.2
09:32:22	343	0.09	56	90	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 5 (leg 2 now @ 500ft)
09:34:00	330	0.09	56	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:36:08	400	0.08	56	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 5
09:36:43	440	0.08	56	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	Run 5.1 to wp44
09:38:00	442	0.09	56	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:40:00	380	0.09	56	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B097

Date: 25/05/2005

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:42:00	300	0.09	56	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:44:00	220	0.09	56	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:46:00	185	0.09	56	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	Note FFSSP dau 16 seconds slow
09:48:00	140	0.08	56	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:50:00	150	0.09	57	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:51:25	210	0.09	57	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 5.1
09:51:54	190	0.09	57	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 5.2 to wp33
09:53:00	800	0.07	57	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:55:00	180	0.09	57	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:57:00	180	0.09	57	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:59:00	140	0.08	57	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:01:00	107	0.08	57	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:03:00	182	0.08	57	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:05:00	140	0.09	57	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:07:00	170	0.09	57	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:09:00	210	0.09	57	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:11:00	265	0.09	57	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:13:00	350	0.08	57	90	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:15:00	586	0.08	57	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:17:00	200	0.08	57	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:19:00	240	0.08	57	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:21:54	220	0.08	58	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 5.1
10:23:06	515	0.07	58	80	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Profile 2 50ft
10:23:15	360	0.07	58	90	0	0	0	0	0	0	100 + run
10:25:09	150	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	500 + run
10:26:40	200	0.07	58	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1000
10:27:45	100	0.07	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	2000 + run
10:30:01	56	0.09	58	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	3000
10:31:20	50	0.08	58	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000 + run
10:33:30	35	0.07	58	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5000
10:34:58	25	0.08	58	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6000 + run
10:35:55	60	0.08	58	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B097

Date: 25/05/2005

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:42:20	400	0.08	58	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 11 @500ft
10:44:00	360	0.08	58	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:46:00	312	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:47:30											End run 11
10:47:34	371	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 11.1
10:49:00	292	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:51:00	244	0.08	58	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:53:00	320	0.09	58	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:55:00	250	0.09	58	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:57:00	280	0.09	58	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:59:00	280	0.09	58	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:00:07	280	0.09	58	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 11.1
11:00:30	271	0.09	58	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 11.2
11:02:00	316	0.09	58	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:04:00	264	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:06:00	239	0.09	58	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:08:00	291	0.09	58	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:10:00	243	0.09	58	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:12:00	278	0.08	58	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:14:00	352	0.09	58	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:16:00	376	0.08	58	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:18:00	282	0.09	58	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:18:24	372	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 11.2
11:18:50	345	0.09	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 11.3
11:20:00	330	0.09	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:22:00	407	0.09	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:24:00	327	0.09	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:26:00	325	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:28:00	298	0.08	58	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:28:40	281	0.08	58	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 11
11:30:18	100	0.08	58	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start profile 3 @50ft
11:30:30	456	0.08	58	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	100ft run

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:31:30	269	0.08	58	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile to 500ft
11:32:05	246	0.08	58	7	0	0	0	0	00	0	500ft run
11:33:07	259	0.08	58	5							Start Profile to 2000
11:33:40	336	0.08	58	10							1000
11:34:36	184	0.08	58	10							End profile @ 2000
11:35:00	200	0.08	58	10							2000ft run
11:37:26	334	0.08	58	10							Start profile to 4000
11:38:17	89	0.08	58	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	3000
11:39:14	50	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000
11:39:47	61	0.08	58	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000ft run
11:40:51	54	0.08	58	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5000
11:42:30	24	0.09	58	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	6000
11:45:02	40	0.08	58	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	6000ft run
11:46:02	35	0.08	58	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of 6000ft run – end of science
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
B097	Continued	After	Refueling	Now a	CLOPAP	flight					
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
14:14:18	689	0.09	86	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start profile 1 @ 50ft
14:15:43	341	0.1	86	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	1000ft
14:16:46	317	0.1	86	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	2000ft
14:17:46	288	0.09	86	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3000ft
14:18:34	84	0.07	86	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000ft
14:19:03	80	0.07	86	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	4500ft end of profile 1
14:26:54	60	0.09	86	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run1 @ 4500ft
14:28:00	54	0.09	86	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:30:00	60	0.08	86	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:32:00	52	0.09	86	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:34:00	61	0.08	86	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:36:00	250	0.09	265	1000	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:38:00	77	0.09	296	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:40:40	64	0.08	481	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:41:30	65	0.09	481	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:44:39	67	0.08	481	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Run 2 @ 4000ft
14:46:00											End run dropping to
14:46:47	41	0.08	481	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Run 3 @3600ft
14:48:00	600	0.27	627	1000	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:50:00	201	0.09	898	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:52:00	230	0.08	917	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:54:00	253	0.09	917	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:56:00	418	0.13	936	1000	0	0	0	0	0	0	
14:58:00	582	0.09	936	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 3 14:58:51
											Seadas restarted to try to get 2d working
15:02:27											Start Run 4 (20)
15:04:00	482	0.1	936	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:06:00	431	0.08	936	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:08:00	398	0.08	936	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:10:00	327	0.09	937	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:12:00	318	0.09	937	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:14:19	471	0.1	937	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 4 (20)
15:18:11	465	0.1	937	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 21 @2300ft
15:20:00	273	0.09	937	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:22:00	276	0.08	937	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:24:00	431	0.09	937	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:26:00	351	0.09	937	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:26:34	491	0.09	937	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of Run 21
15:30:59	478	0.08	937	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 22 4600ft
15:32:00	233	0.08	937	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:34:00	120	0.08	937	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:36:00	60	0.08	937	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:38:00	64	0.08	937	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:38:25	54	0.08	937	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 22dir *.dat

Flight No:

B097

Date:

25 / 05 / 05

Operator:

S W HEATH + M. SMITH

Run No	Disk No 1	Disk No 2	Disk No 3	Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
R1			↻	TNPT 1	080405	083508		746	Transit to WP47
R1				TPB 1	080405	083508		290	@ FL100
P1 → R4.2				TNPT 2	083800	092515		0	Blank - all valves closed
P1 → R4.2				TPB 2	083800	092408		0	Blank
R4.2 → R5.1				TNPT 3	092703	095125		434	Ed of WP46, FL25 & 500ft
R4.2 → R5.1				TPB 3	092703	095125		779	
R11 → R11.2				TNPT 4	104301	111107		577	} from WP 40 } to just ~ 6 mins before WP80
R11 → R11.2				TPB 4	104301	111107		1084	
R11.2 → R11.3				TNPT 5	111342	112904		270	Last AMPER sample as
R11.2 → R11.3				TPB 5	111342	112904		517	profile next then Newcastle
									AMPER

Note! O-rings are not fitted in all the supplied filter packs so holders not closing as tight as they should. This is especially the case for the bottom inlet holder. (TPB)

Need to ensure that 30-rings per filter pack are fitted for future flights

↳ checked and all o-rings fitted!

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B097
Date: 25/05/2005

Campaign Name: AMPEP/
CLOPAP
Operator: J. Hopkins
(York)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
7:56:00	7:57:00	1	On way up to 10000 ft to WP 47	3.00
8:06:43	8:07:43	2	Run 1 at 10000 ft	3.00
8:14:01	8:15:01	3	Run 1 at 10000 ft	3.00
8:21:01	8:22:01	4	Run 1 at 10000 ft	
8:32:00	8:33:00	5	Run 1 at 10000 ft	3.01
-08:34:50			End of run 1	
8:47:06			Profile 1.1 1500 ft to 2000 ft	
			2000 ft 1 min level run	
			Profile 1.2 2000 ft to 3000 ft	
			3000 ft to 4000 ft	
			4000 ft 1 min level run	
			4000 ft to 6000 ft	
			6000 ft level run	
9:05:00	9:06:00	6	Run 4 at 2500 ft, FL2.5 flying overland Devon/Cornwall	3.26
9:13:58			Run 4.1 toward WP46	
9:17:49	9:18:49	7	Run 4.1 at 2500 ft- overland (??) above cloud	3.26
9:28:00	9:29:00	8	Run 4.2 at 2500 ft (sampled during start of descent to 500 ft)	3.26
9:32:25			Level run 5 at 500 ft	
9:36:35	9:37:35	9	Run 5.1 at 500 ft (sampled at start of run) heading toward WP44	3.31
9:40:30	9:41:30	10	Run 5.1 at 500 ft	3.31
9:45:36	9:46:36	11	Fast Fill Run 5.1 at 500 ft	3.31
9:51:10	9:52:10	12	Run 5.51 to 5.52 Filling on the turn (i.e. at WP44)	3.31
9:53:50	9:54:50	13	Fast Fill Run 5.2 at 500 ft	3.31
9:56:31	9:57:31	14	Fast Fill Run 5.2 at 500 ft	3.31
10:00:20	10:01:20	15	Fast Fill Run 5.2 at 500 ft	3.31

10:09:20	10:10:20	16	Fast Fill Run 5 at 500 ft	3.31
10:15:10	10:16:10	17	Fast Fill Run 5 at 500 ft	3.31
10:18:01	10:19:01	18	Fast Fill Run 5 at 500 ft	3.31
10:20:00			End of run 1	
			Descend to 50 ft	
			Up to 100 ft for 1 min	
			100 ft to 500 ft	
			Run at 500 ft for 1 min	
			500 ft to 2000 ft	
			Run at 2000 ft	
			2000 ft to 4000 ft	
			Run at 4000 ft	
			4000 ft to 6000 ft	
			Run at 6000 ft for 1 min	
			Descend to 500 ft	
10:46:02	10:47:02	19	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
10:47:59	10:48:59	20	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	1.37
			*** Both case 7 and 6 were flushing!***	
10:49:12		21	Pressure only reaching 1.38 bar so re-start WAS software	
10:52:00	10:53:00	22	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
10:54:00	10:55:00	23	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
10:57:01	10:58:01	24	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
11:01:36	11:02:36	25	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
11:03:21	11:04:21	26	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
11:05:37	11:06:37	27	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
11:08:34	11:09:34	28	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
11:13:45	11:14:45	29	Fast Fill run at 500 ft	3.31
11:16:40	11:17:40	30	Fast Fill run at 500 ft polluted sample	3.31
11:23:22	11:24:22	31	Run 11.3 at 500 ft	3.31
			Land at Newcastle airport; Take off from Newcastle	

Locked out cases 7, 6, 4 and all of case 5 except bottle 32

14:14:18

Descend to 50 ft

Profile 4 - 50 ft to top of cloud (4500 ft)

Not much cloud further out to sea. Moving back towards land before starting.

14:28:30

14:29:30

41

Run at 4500 ft above cloud (??- not much if any cloud below)

3.19

14:32:42

14:33:42

42

Run at 4500 ft above cloud?

3.19

14:40:18

14:41:18

43

Run at 4500 ft- extended run since in cloude/above cloud

3.19

14:44:38

Run at 4500 ft in cloud

14:46:31

14:47:31

44

Run at 4000 ft (dropped to 3600 ft near start of sample to catch the cloud)

3.21

14:51:00

14:51:30

45

Fast Fill for 30 s Run at 3600 ft in cloud

3.17

15:06:00

15:07:00

46

Run at 2300 ft below cloud

3.25

15:09:51

15:10:51

47

Run at 2300 ft below cloud

3.25

15:20:11

15:20:41

48

Fast Fill for 30 s Run at 2300 ft below cloud

3.24

15:34:00

15:35:00

32

Run 22 at 4600 ft (PRESSURE DIDN'T DROP AT START OF FILLING- BOTTLE POSSIBLY NOT FILLED)

3.18**

Flight No. 8097a Route

Date 25/5/05 Take Off 8.45 AM

Bag Samplers: D. Polson A. McDonald

Sheet No. 001

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-342	08.02.00	08.02.30	51.8N	2.4W	height 10,000 ft
05-435	08.05.00	08.05.30	51.8N	2.7W	10,000 ft
05-173	08.07.00	08.07.30	51.7N	2.9W	"
05-290	08.10.00	08.10.30			"
05-424	08.13.00	08.13.27			"
05-285	08.16.00	08.16.30	51.4N	3.7W	"
05-282	08.19.00	08.19.30			"
05-557	08.22.00	08.22.40			"
05-203	08.26.00	08.26.50	51.1N	4.6W	"
05-241	08.28.00	08.28.30			"
05-363	08.29.00	08.29.30			"
05-293	08.30.00	08.30.30	50.9N	4.9W	"
05-318	08.33.00	08.33.30			"
05-172	08.36.00	08.36.30			"
05-242	08.47.07	08.47.30			profile 1.1 - 15.2 km
05-518	08.47.48	08.48.17			2 ft
05-457	08.48.48	08.49.18			profile 1.2
05-496	08.50.18	08.50.48			6 ft
05-499	08.51.19	08.51.49			6 ft
05-441	08.52.25	08.52.50			profile 1.3 4-6W
05-436	08.55.00	08.55.30			6 kft
05-492	08.52.00	08.57.32	50.8N	4.9W	descent from 6 kft
05-444	08.58.00	08.58.25			"
05-271	08.59.00	08.59.25			
05-508	09.00.00	09.00.25			2.5 kft
05-516	09.01.00	09.01.30			"
05-251	09.02.00	09.02.35			flam side too low
05-517	09.03.00	09.03.30			
05-359	09.04.00	09.04.30			
05-402	09.05.00	09.05.20	50.6N	4.4W	2.5 kft
05-439	09.06.00	09.06.30			
05-558	09.07.00	09.07.30			
05-430	09.08.00	09.08.30			
05-498	09.09.00	09.09.30			
05-415	09.10.00	09.10.30			
05-250	09.11.00	09.11.30	50.3	4.1W	
05-464	09.12.00	09.12.30			
05-245	09.13.00	09.13.30			
05-005	09.16.00	09.16.30			st. num 4.1
05-454	09.15.00	09.15.30			
05-451	09.16.00	09.16.30			

Flight No. 13097aRoute Date 23/5/05Take Off Bag Samplers: 08 A.M.Sheet No. 002

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-043	09:17:00	09:17:30	50.1N	5.8W	
421	18:00	18:30			
256	19:00	19:30			
285	20:00	20:30			
406	21:00	21:30			
288	22:00	22:30			end run 4.1
426	22:30	23:30			
493	24:00	24:30			
411	25:00	25:30			2.5 km
494	26:00	26:30			
408	27:00	27:30			
434	28:00	28:30	50.0N	2.7W	end run 4.2
511	29:00	29:30			500 ft descent to
555	30:00	30:30			↓
520	31:00	31:30			
292	32:00	32:30			0.5 km (0.5 km)
545	33:00	33:30			
551	34:00	34:30			
425	35:00	35:30			
429	36:00	36:30			
489	32:15 30:00	37:40	50.0N	1.9W	
552	38:00	38:30			
254	39:00	39:30			
353	40:00	40:30			
524	41:00	41:30			
455	42:00	42:30			
232	43:00	43:30			
214	44:00	44:30			
253	45:00	45:30			
470	46:00	46:30			
314	47:00	47:30	50.4N	1.2W	
369	48:00	48:30			
370	49:00	49:30			
252	50:00	50:30			
249	51:00	51:30			
310	52:00	52:30			
248	53:00	53:30			
247	54:00	54:30			
246	55:00	55:30			
245	56:00	56:30			
244	57:00	57:30			

Flight No. B097aRoute Date 25/5/05Take Off 8.45 AMBag Samplers: DP AMSheet No. 003

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05028	09:58:00	09:58:30	50.6N	0.3W	0.5 kft - (1000ft)
180	11:59:00	11:59:30			
179	10:00:00	10:00:30			
178	10:01:00	10:01:30			
177	10:02:00	10:02:30			
176	10:03:00	10:03:30			
175	10:04:00	10:04:30			
009	11:05:00	11:05:30			
008	06:00	06:30	50.6N	0.2E	0.5 kft
007	07:00	07:30			
006	08:00	08:30			
004	09:00	09:30			
003	10:00	10:30			
002	11:00	11:30			
001	12:00	12:30			
011	13:00	13:30			
023	14:00	14:30			
022	15:00	15:30			
021	16:00	16:30			
030	17:00	17:30	50.9N	1.1E	0.5 kft
029	18:00	18:30			
027	19:00	19:30			
026	20:00	20:30			
025	21:00	21:30			descent to
024	23:02	23:32			starting 70 ft.
016	23:43	24:13			100 ft.
018	24:25	24:55			100 - 500 ft.
012	25:08	25:38			500 ft.
015	26:00	26:30			500 - 2000 ft.
014	27:54	28:24			2000 ft.
013	29:00	30:07			2000 - ft 4000 ft
012	30:25	30:55			- " - -
042	31:30	32:00			4000 ft.
041	32:40	33:10			4000 - 6000 ft.
050	35:00	35:30			6000 ft.
049	37:00	37:30			descent from 6000 ft.
048	38:00	38:30	52.1N	1.7E	- " - -
047	39:00	39:30			- " - -
046	40:00	40:30			- " - -
045	41:00	41:30			
044	42:00	42:30			

Flight No. BD97aRoute Date 25/5/65Take Off 8.45 BSTBag Samplers: D.P. A.M.Sheet No. 004

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-020	10:43:00	10:43:30	52.4N	1.7E	06/200H 500H
05-019	10:44:00	10:44:30			
056	45:00	45:30			
055	46:00	46:30			
054	47:00	47:30			
053	48:00	48:30			
052	49:00	49:30			
051	50:00	50:30			
050	51:00	51:30			
059	52:00	52:30			
058	53:00	53:30			
057	54:00	54:30			
070	55:00	55:30			
069	56:00	56:30			
068	57:00	57:30			
067	58:00	58:30			
066	59:00	59:30			
065	11:00:00	11:00:30	53.4N	1.4E	
064	11:01:00	11:01:30			
063	11:02:00	11:02:30			
062	11:03:00	11:03:30			suspect bag
061	11:04:00	11:04:30			
076	11:05:00	11:05:30			
077	11:06:00	11:06:30			
078	11:07:00	11:07:30			
079	11:08:00	11:08:30			
080	11:09:00	11:09:30			
075	11:10:00	11:10:30	53.7N	0.7E	~500H
074	11:11:00	11:11:30			
090	11:12:00	11:12:30			
073	11:13:00	11:13:30			
072	11:14:00	11:14:30			
071	11:15:00	11:15:30			
089	16:00	16:30			
088	17:00	17:30			
087	18:00	18:30			
086	19:00	19:30			
085	20:00	20:30			
084	21:00	21:30			
083	22:00	22:30			
082	23:00	23:30			

5th May 07

Bu97a

Flying with Sunny on AMS lower on Mission

Bu97a = AMOEP

Bu97b = CLUPAP

0500 - Power on to aircraft.

0510 - All pumps 100% → heater on.

0700 - filament on @ 0.05mA

→ looks good

(multiplier ~~at~~ raised from 2 S → 2.0kV.)

0740 - Tuning

Def	New	
Def In	12	18
Def Out	9	10
HB	-6.35	0.00
Foc	14.35	15
Ext	238	230

OK

0745 - EM cal.....

WB 1.500
Gain 2.02e6

0750 - main range cal
take main for IE cal

0800 - IE cal. $IE = 1.01 \times 10^{-10}$ P. 0.00 2.00

1.00 10.00 2.00 P. 0.00 2.00

1.00 10.00 2.00

0820 - CR on high flow
CR logging in subview
AMS net closed
SE region 3 mother waves from 5020-5030 Hz

0835 - m/z line 14, 16, 30, 40, 42, 43, 44, 57 + 3'
Charged net!

0830 - See time to match noise

1300 - landed at ~~CR~~ Newcastle, with AMS net closed
Called mum and wished her happy birthday

love run 5033

All pump 100%
Kicker Amp: 5000
Compressor 2000 ton

BO97h CLAPAR

Output from run 5034:

Mission Starter: Captain K.N. Bower

ie approx 0145 take off

14:42 AMS on Col

15:10 Dead! close over
Do not put up 40 J. recheck 5030
Do not check 5035.
End of

0820 - CR on high flow
CR logging in subview
AMS net closed
SE region 3 motor wires from 5020 + 5300, etc

0835 - m/z line 14, 16, 30, 40, 42, 43, 44, 57 + 3'
Charged net!

0830 - See time to match noise

1300 - landed at ~~CR~~ Newcastle, with AMS net closed
Called mum and wished her happy birthday

love from SO33

All pump 100%
Kicker Amp: 5000
Compressor 2000 ton

BO97h CLOAP

Output from ran SO34:

Mission Starter: Captain K.N. Bower

ie approx 0145 take off

14:42 AMS on Col

15:10 Dead! close over
Do not put up 40 J. recheck 500
Do not check 5000.
End of

The video showed primary data showing
the

Memory Dump

The screen did
manage to restart R.
Note high cabin temperatures - possible cause of
melting system

Spared 17 R ... seems ok

Goodnight.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B097**

Date: 25/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS		y
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		y
WAS	Y	y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B097

Date: 25/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. CCN data problem appears cleared
3. SID1 fault-finding during flight.
4. SID2 u/s
5. INC under test
6. AMS; pc died late in flight (overheat)
7. otherwise ops normal:
 8. Filters (see log note on O rings)
 9. Cloud Physics
 10. core chem
 11. NOxy
 12. PTRMS
 13. CCN
 14. Bag filling
 15. WAS

Aircraft

1. High cabin temperature forward (33C) reported, cool aft

